

Mechanical combined with chemical recycling for vacuum-infused acrylate-based composites reinforced by glass and basalt fabrics

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CONTEXT

- Development of semi-structural composites for the automotive industry based on fabrics by vacuum infusion.
- Study of the end of life of these composites by considering a mixed recycling combining mechanical grinding and dissolution.

GOALS

- Satisfy the requirements of the automotive sector in terms of durability and recyclability.
- Circular economy approach: aiming at end-of-life recycling.

DEFINITIONS

refG	Reference Glass fibers
G/S G	Ground Glass fibers (fraction >2mm)
G/S/D G	Ground, Sieved and Dissolved Glass fibers (fraction >2mm)
refB	Reference Basalt fibers
G B	Ground Basalt fibers
G/D B	Ground and Dissolved Basalt fibers

MATERIALS

First-generation composites to be recycled:

- Plain basalt fabrics (220 g/m²), Basaltex
 - Plain glass fabrics (202 g/m²), M.C. Technics
 - Elium@150 resin, Arkema
- Vacuum infused thermoplastic composites (10 plies)

Second-generation composites:

- Polyamide 6 Akulon F223-D, DSM Engineering Materials.
- Reference short glass fibers (4.5 mm; OCV) and short basalt fibers (3.2 mm; Basaltex).
- Ground/dissolved first-generation composites

METHODOLOGY

CHARACTERISATION OF PA6/SHORT FIBERS COMPOSITES

Flexural and tensile strengths

Flexural properties of G/D better than G except for glass. Comparable flexural moduli for reference and G/D basalt.

Grinding/dissolution samples have better tensile properties than grinding ones. Even better Young's modulus for G/D than reference in both cases of glass and basalt.

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

Differential Scanning Calorimetry

	Wf (%)	Xc (%)
PA6	-	42.77 ± 12.25
refG	19.30 ± 0.49	22.76 ± 1.93
G/S G	13.13 ± 0.59	25.01 ± 2.24
G/S/D G	18.52 ± 0.32	26.42 ± 1.67
refB	18.34 ± 1.45	27.14 ± 1.50
GB	13.45 ± 1.45	25.00 ± 1.66
G/D B	19.50 ± 0.28	27.22 ± 0.91

Scanning Electron Microscope

- Average fiber length of 200 μm.
- Incorporation of fibers in PA6 decreases Xc proportionally to the fiber content in the composite.
- Good fiber-matrix adhesion thanks to the presence of residual Elium@150 resin on the fiber surface but lower than reference => Increase of E' in DMA

Fiber length measurement

CONCLUSION

- Coupling grinding and dissolution could be considered as an efficient approach to recycle basalt/glass Elium@150 composites:
- Dissolution increases the fiber content in the second-generation composite.
 - The presence of residual resin improves fiber-matrix adhesion (mechanical adhesion, physico-chemical wetting adhesion).
 - Tensile properties are increased (Young's modulus, E).

=> Reincorporation of ground and dissolved basalt or glass fibers into PA6 thermoplastic matrix is an interesting way to valorize end-of-life plain thermoplastic composites.